

ISic0956

I.Sicily inscription 0956

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Maria de Gesu

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 85

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Κυριακοῦ καὶ Σαλ
2. βίας παιδίον πεδὶν ἐνθά
3. δε κεῖται ὀνόματι
4. Κυριακός ἔζησεν
5. ἔτη τρία μῆνας δέ κα ἡμέρας πέντε
7. εἰς ἑῶνα μετὰ τῷ
8. ν ἀγίων αὐτοῦ τὸ
9. ψυχὴν ἐν ὀνόμα
10. τι · Ἰησοῦ Π(ιστοῦ) Κυριακῆ
11. ἡ καλώνυμος ἔζη
12. σεν καὶ αὐτὴ ἔτη γ

Apparatus

Text of IG

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492586

EDCS 39102113

PHI 140437

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0139 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Agnello, S.L. 1953. Silloge di iscrizioni paleocristiane della Sicilia. Rome. At no.44

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